

Operators on Single Valued Trapezoidal Neutrosophic Numbers and SVTN-Group Decision Making

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Abstract: In this paper, we first introduce single valued trapezoidal neutrosophic (SVTN) numbers with their properties. We then define some operations and distances of the SVTN-numbers. Based on these new operations, we also define some aggregation operators, including SVTN-ordered weighted geometric operator, SVTN-hybrid geometric operator, SVTN-ordered weighted arithmetic operator and SVTN-hybrid arithmetic operator. We then examine the properties of these SVTN-information aggregation operators. By using the SVTN-weighted geometric operator and SVTN-hybrid geometric operator, we also define a multi attribute group decision making method, called SVTN-group decision making method. We finally give an illustrative example and comparative analysis to verify the developed method and to demonstrate its practicality and effectiveness.

Keywords: Single valued neutrosophic sets, neutrosophic numbers, trapezoidal neutrosophic numbers, SVTN-numbers, SVTN-group decision making.

1 Introduction

In real decision making, there usually are many multiple attribute group decision making (MAGDM) problems. Due to the ambiguity of people's thinking and the complexity of objective things, the attribute values of the MAGDM problems cannot always be expressed by exact and crisp values and it may be easier to describe them by neutrosophic information. Zadeh [77] initiated fuzzy set theory. It is one of the most effective tools for processing fuzzy information which has only one membership, and is unable to express non-membership. Therefore, Atanassov [3] presented the intuitionistic fuzzy sets by adding a nonmembership function. Also, Atanassov and Gargov [4] proposed the interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy set by extending the membership function and nonmembership function to the interval numbers. These sets can only handle incomplete information, not the indeterminate information and inconsistent information. For this reason, Smarandache [53, 54, 55] introduced a new concept that is called neutrosophic set by adding an independent indeterminacy-membership on the basis of intuitionistic fuzzy sets from philosophical point of view, which is a generalization of the concepts of classical sets, probability sets, rough sets [43], fuzzy sets [77, 23], intuitionistic fuzzy sets [3], paraconsistent sets, dialetheist sets, paradoxist sets and tautological sets. In theory of neutrosophic sets, truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership and falsity-membership are represented independently. Also, Wang et al. [62] proposed the interval neutrosophic sets by extending the truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership, and falsity-membership functions to interval numbers. After

Smarandache, Broumi et al. [5, 6, 7], Biswas et al. [8, 9, 10, 11, 12, 13, 14, 15], Kahraman and Otay [32], Mondal et al. [35, 36, 37, 38, 39, 40] and Pramanik et al. [44, 45, 46, 47] studied on some decision making problems based on neutrosophic information. Recently, fuzzy and neutrosophic models have been studied by many authors, such as [1, 2, 19, 20, 28, 29, 30, 48, 49, 50, 52, 57, 58, 62, 63, 80, 81, 82, 83].

Gani et al. [27] presented a method called weighted average rating method for solving group decision making problem by using an intuitionistic trapezoidal fuzzy hybrid aggregation operator. Wan et al. [65] investigated MAGDM problems, in which the ratings of alternatives are expressed with triangular intuitionistic fuzzy numbers. Wei [66, 67], introduced some new group decision making methods by developing aggregation operators with intuitionistic fuzzy information. Xu and Yager [60], presented some new geometric aggregation operators, such as intuitionistic fuzzy weighted geometric operator, intuitionistic fuzzy ordered weighted geometric operator, and intuitionistic fuzzy hybrid geometric operator. Wu and Cao [68] developed some geometric aggregation operators with intuitionistic trapezoidal fuzzy numbers and examined their desired properties. Power average operator of real numbers is extended to four kinds of power average operators of trapezoidal intuitionistic fuzzy numbers by Wan [64]. Farhadinia and Ban [25] initiated a novel method to extend a similarity measure of generalized trapezoidal fuzzy numbers to similarity measures of generalized trapezoidal intuitionistic fuzzy numbers and generalized interval-valued trapezoidal fuzzy numbers. Ye [71] proposed an extended technique for order preference by similarity to ideal solution method for group decision making with interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy numbers to solve the partner selection problem under incomplete and uncertain information environment. Recently, some intuitionistic models with intuitionistic values have been studied by many authors. For example, on intuitionistic fuzzy sets [26, 59, 76], on interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy sets [16, 26], interval-valued intuitionistic trapezoidal fuzzy numbers [26, 69], on triangular intuitionistic fuzzy number [17, 24, 26, 33, 34, 61, 78], on trapezoidal intuitionistic fuzzy numbers [18, 26, 31, 34, 41, 42, 51, 72, 75, 79], on generalized trapezoidal fuzzy numbers, on generalized trapezoidal intuitionistic fuzzy numbers and generalized interval-valued trapezoidal fuzzy numbers [25].

A neutrosophic set can handle a incomplete, indeterminate and inconsistent information from philosophical point of view. Ye [74] and Subas, [56] introduced single valued neutrosophic numbers, which is a generalization of fuzzy numbers and intuitionistic fuzzy numbers. The neutrosophic numbers are special single valued neutrosophic sets on the real number sets, which are useful to deal with ill-known quantities in decision data and decision making problems themselves. Then, Ye [73] and Deli and Subas, [21, 22] developed new methods on single valued neutrosophic numbers based on multi-criteria decision making problem. But, multi-criteria group decision making problem has not yet been studied.

The paper is organized as follows. In the next section, we give some basic definitions and properties of single valued trapezoidal neutrosophic (SVTN) numbers. In Section 3, some operations for SVTN-numbers and distance between two SVTN-number are presented. In Section 4, we introduce some new geometric aggregation operators, including SVTN-ordered weighted geometric operator, SVTN-hybrid geometric operator, SVTN-ordered weighted arithmetic operator and SVTN-hybrid arithmetic operator. In Section 5, we develop a group decision making method, so called SVTN-group decision making method to solve MAGDM problems based on the SVTN-weighted geometric operator and the SVTN-hybrid geometric operators. We then present an illustrative example to verify the developed method and to demonstrate its practicality. In Section 6 we give a comparative analysis. In Section 7, we conclude the paper and give some remarks.

2 Preliminary

In this section, some basic concepts and definitions on fuzzy sets, intuitionistic fuzzy sets, neutrosophic sets, single valued neutrosophic sets and single valued neutrosophic numbers are given.

Definition 2.1. [77] Let E be a universe. Then, a fuzzy set X over E is defined by

$$X = \{(\mu_X(x)/x) : x \in E\}$$

where $\mu_X : E \rightarrow [0,1]$ is called membership function of X . For each $x \in E$, the value $\mu_X(x)$ represents the degree of x belonging to the fuzzy set X .

Definition 2.2. [3] Let E be a universe. Then, an intuitionistic fuzzy set K over E is defined by

$$K = \{< x, \mu_K(x), \gamma_K(x) > : x \in E\}$$

where $\mu_K : E \rightarrow [0, 1]$ and $\gamma_K : E \rightarrow [0, 1]$ such that $0 \leq \mu_K(x) + \gamma_K(x) \leq 1$ for any $x \in E$. For each $x \in E$, the values $\mu_K(x)$ and $\gamma_K(x)$ are the degree of membership and degree of non-membership of x , respectively.

Definition 2.3. [54] Let E be a universe. Then, a neutrosophic set A over E is defined by

$$A = \{< x, (T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x)) > : x \in E\}.$$

where $T_A(x)$, $I_A(x)$ and $F_A(x)$ are called truth-membership function, indeterminacy-membership function and falsity-membership function, respectively. They are respectively defined by $T_A : E \rightarrow]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$, $I_A : E \rightarrow]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$, $F_A : E \rightarrow]^{-}0, 1^{+}[$ such that $0^{-} \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3^{+}$.

Definition 2.4. [63] Let E be a universe. Then, a single valued neutrosophic set over E is a neutrosophic set over E , but the truth-membership function, indeterminacy-membership function and falsity-membership function are respectively defined by

$$T_A : E \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad I_A : E \rightarrow [0, 1], \quad F_A : E \rightarrow [0, 1]$$

such that $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3$.

Definition 2.5. [22, 56] A single valued trapezoidal neutrosophic number $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1); w_{\tilde{a}}, u_{\tilde{a}}, y_{\tilde{a}} \rangle$ is a special neutrosophic set on the real number set R , whose truth-membership, indeterminacy-membership, and a falsity-membership are given as follows:

$$\mu_{\tilde{a}}(x) = \begin{cases} (x - a_1)w_{\tilde{a}}/(b_1 - a_1), & (a_1 \leq x < b_1) \\ w_{\tilde{a}}, & (b_1 \leq x \leq c_1) \\ (d_1 - x)w_{\tilde{a}}/(d_1 - c_1), & (c_1 < x \leq d_1) \\ 0, & otherwise, \end{cases}$$

$$\nu_{\tilde{a}}(x) = \begin{cases} (b_1 - x + u_{\tilde{a}}(x - a_1))/(b_1 - a_1), & (a_1 \leq x < b_1) \\ u_{\tilde{a}}, & (b_1 \leq x \leq c_1) \\ (x - c_1 + u_{\tilde{a}}(d_1 - x))/(d_1 - c_1), & (c_1 < x \leq d_1) \\ 1, & otherwise \end{cases}$$

and

$$\lambda_{\tilde{a}}(x) = \begin{cases} (b_1 - x + y_{\tilde{a}}(x - a_1))/(b_1 - a_1), & (a_1 \leq x < b_1) \\ y_{\tilde{a}}, & (b_1 \leq x \leq c_1) \\ (x - c_1 + y_{\tilde{a}}(d_1 - x))/(d_1 - c_1), & (c_1 < x \leq d_1) \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

respectively.

Sometimes, we use the $\tilde{a}_i = \langle (a_i, b_i, c_i, d_i); w_i, u_i, y_i \rangle$, instead of $\tilde{a}_i = \langle (a_i, b_i, c_i, d_i); w_{\tilde{a}_i}, u_{\tilde{a}_i}, y_{\tilde{a}_i} \rangle$.

Note that the single valued trapezoidal neutrosophic number is abbreviated as SVTN-number and the set of all SVTN-numbers on R will be denoted by Ω .

3 Operations and Distances of SVTN-Numbers

In this section, we give operations and distances of SVTN-numbers and investigate their related properties.

Definition 3.1. [73] Let $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1); w_{\tilde{a}}, u_{\tilde{a}}, y_{\tilde{a}} \rangle$, $\tilde{b} = \langle (a_2, b_2, c_2, d_2); w_{\tilde{b}}, u_{\tilde{b}}, y_{\tilde{b}} \rangle \in \Omega$ and $\gamma \geq 0$ be any real number. Then,

1. $\tilde{a} \oplus \tilde{b} = \langle (a_1 + a_2, b_1 + b_2, c_1 + c_2, d_1 + d_2); w_{\tilde{a}} + w_{\tilde{b}} - w_{\tilde{a}}w_{\tilde{b}}, u_{\tilde{a}}u_{\tilde{b}}, y_{\tilde{a}}y_{\tilde{b}} \rangle$
2. $\tilde{a} \otimes \tilde{b} = \langle (a_1a_2, b_1b_2, c_1c_2, d_1d_2); w_{\tilde{a}}w_{\tilde{b}}, u_{\tilde{a}} + u_{\tilde{b}} - u_{\tilde{a}}u_{\tilde{b}}, y_{\tilde{a}} + y_{\tilde{b}} - y_{\tilde{a}}y_{\tilde{b}} \rangle$
3. $\gamma\tilde{a} = \langle (\gamma a_1, \gamma b_1, \gamma c_1, \gamma d_1); 1 - (1 - w_{\tilde{a}})^\gamma, u_{\tilde{a}}^\gamma, y_{\tilde{a}}^\gamma \rangle$
4. $\tilde{a}^\gamma = \langle (a_1^\gamma, b_1^\gamma, c_1^\gamma, d_1^\gamma); w_{\tilde{a}}^\gamma, 1 - (1 - u_{\tilde{a}})^\gamma, 1 - (1 - y_{\tilde{a}})^\gamma \rangle$

Theorem 3.2. Let $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1); w_1, u_1, y_1 \rangle$, $\tilde{b} = \langle (a_2, b_2, c_2, d_2); w_2, u_2, y_2 \rangle \in \Omega$. Then, $\tilde{a} \oplus \tilde{b}$, $\tilde{a} \otimes \tilde{b}$, $\gamma\tilde{a}$ and \tilde{a}^γ are also SVTN-numbers.

Proof: It is easy from Definition 3.1.

Theorem 3.3. Let $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1); w_1, u_1, y_1 \rangle$, $\tilde{b} = \langle (a_2, b_2, c_2, d_2); w_2, u_2, y_2 \rangle$, $\tilde{c} = \langle (a_3, b_3, c_3, d_3); w_3, u_3, y_3 \rangle \in \Omega$ and $\gamma, \gamma_1, \gamma_2$ be positive real numbers. Then, the followings are valid.

1. $\tilde{a} \oplus \tilde{b} = \tilde{b} \oplus \tilde{a}$
2. $\tilde{a} \otimes \tilde{b} = \tilde{b} \otimes \tilde{a}$
3. $(\tilde{a} \otimes \tilde{b}) \otimes \tilde{c} = \tilde{a} \otimes (\tilde{b} \otimes \tilde{c})$
4. $(\tilde{a} \oplus \tilde{b}) \oplus \tilde{c} = \tilde{a} \oplus (\tilde{b} \oplus \tilde{c})$
5. $\tilde{a} \otimes (\tilde{b} \oplus \tilde{c}) = (\tilde{a} \otimes \tilde{b}) \oplus (\tilde{a} \otimes \tilde{c})$
6. $(\tilde{a} \otimes \tilde{b})^\gamma = \tilde{b}^\gamma \otimes \tilde{a}_1^\gamma$
7. $\tilde{a}^{\gamma_1} \otimes \tilde{a}^{\gamma_2} = \tilde{a}^{(\gamma_1 + \gamma_2)}$ or $\tilde{b}^{\gamma_1} \otimes \tilde{b}^{\gamma_2} = \tilde{b}^{(\gamma_1 + \gamma_2)}$

Proof: It is easy from Definition 3.1.

Definition 3.4. Let $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1); w_1, u_1, y_1 \rangle$, $\tilde{b} = \langle (a_2, b_2, c_2, d_2); w_2, u_2, y_2 \rangle \in \Omega$. Then, the distance between \tilde{a} and \tilde{b} is defined by

$$d_h(\tilde{a}, \tilde{b}) = \frac{1}{6} (|(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)a_1 - (1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)a_2| + |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)b_1 - (1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)b_2| + |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)c_1 - (1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)c_2| + |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)d_1 - (1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)d_2|)$$

Example 3.5. Assume that $\tilde{a} = \langle (1, 4, 5, 6); 0.3, 0.4, 0.7 \rangle$, $\tilde{b} = \langle (1, 2, 5, 7); 0.7, 0.5, 0.1 \rangle \in \Omega$. Then, the distance of \tilde{a} and \tilde{b} is computed by

$$d_h(\tilde{a}, \tilde{b}) = \frac{1}{6} (|(1 + 0.3 - 0.4 - 0.7)1 - (1 + 0.7 - 0.5 - 0.1)1| + |(1 + 0.3 - 0.4 - 0.7)4 - (1 + 0.7 - 0.5 - 0.1)2| + |(1 + 0.3 - 0.4 - 0.7)5 - (1 + 0.7 - 0.5 - 0.1)5| + |(1 + 0.3 - 0.4 - 0.7)6 - (1 + 0.7 - 0.5 - 0.1)7|) \cong 7.78$$

Theorem 3.6. Let $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1); w_1, u_1, y_1 \rangle$, $\tilde{b} = \langle (a_2, b_2, c_2, d_2); w_2, u_2, y_2 \rangle \in \Omega$. Then, $d_h(\tilde{a}, \tilde{b})$ meet the nonnegative, symmetric and triangle inequality (or metric).

Proof: Clearly, the $d_h(\tilde{a}, \tilde{b})$ meet the nonnegative, symmetric properties. For $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1); w_1, u_1, y_1 \rangle$, $\tilde{b} = \langle (a_2, b_2, c_2, d_2); w_2, u_2, y_2 \rangle$, $\tilde{c} = \langle (a_3, b_3, c_3, d_3); w_3, u_3, y_3 \rangle \in \Omega$, to prove the triangle inequality, since

$$\begin{aligned} & |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)a_1 - (1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)a_2| + |(1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)a_2 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)a_3| \\ & \geq |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)a_1 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)a_3| \\ & |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)b_1 - (1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)b_2| + |(1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)b_2 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)b_3| \\ & \geq |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)b_1 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)b_3| \\ & |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)c_1 - (1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)c_2| + |(1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)c_2 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)c_3| \\ & \geq |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)c_1 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)c_3| \\ & |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)d_1 - (1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)d_2| + |(1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)d_2 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)d_3| \\ & \geq |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)d_1 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)d_3| \end{aligned}$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned}
& |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)a_1 - (1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)a_2| + \\
& |(1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)a_2 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)a_3| \\
& + |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)b_1 - (1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)b_2| + \\
& |(1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)b_2 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)b_3| \\
& + |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)c_1 - (1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)c_2| + \\
& |(1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)c_2 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)c_3| \\
& + |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)d_1 - (1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)d_2| + \\
& |(1 + w_2 - u_2 - y_2)d_2 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)d_3| \\
& \geq |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)a_1 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)a_3| + \\
& |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)b_1 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)b_3| \\
& + |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)c_1 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)c_3| + \\
& |(1 + w_1 - u_1 - y_1)d_1 - (1 + w_3 - u_3 - y_3)d_3|
\end{aligned}$$

and then,

$$d_h(\tilde{a}, \tilde{b}) + d_h(\tilde{b}, \tilde{c}) \geq d_h(\tilde{a}, \tilde{c})$$

Definition 3.7. [56] Let $\tilde{a} = \langle (a_1, b_1, c_1, d_1); w_1, u_1, y_1 \rangle \in \Omega$. Then, a normalized SVTN-number of \tilde{a} is defined by

$$\langle (\frac{a_1}{a_1+b_1+c_1+d_1}, \frac{b_1}{a_1+b_1+c_1+d_1}, \frac{c_1}{a_1+b_1+c_1+d_1}, \frac{d_1}{a_1+b_1+c_1+d_1}); w_1, u_1, y_1 \rangle$$

Example 3.8. Assume that $\tilde{a} = \langle (1, 4, 5, 10); 0.3, 0.4, 0.7 \rangle \in \Omega$. Then, a normalized SVTN-number of \tilde{a} is computed as

$$\langle (0.05, 0.2, 0.25, 0.5); 0.3, 0.4, 0.7 \rangle$$

Definition 3.9. The SVTN-numbers $\tilde{a}^+ = \langle (1, 1, 1, 1); 1, 0, 0 \rangle$, $\tilde{a}_s^+ = \langle (1, 1, 1, 1); 1, 1, 0 \rangle$, $\tilde{a}^- = \langle (0, 0, 0, 0); 0, 1, 1 \rangle$ and $\tilde{a}_s^- = \langle (0, 0, 0, 0); 0, 0, 1 \rangle$ are called SVTN-positive ideal solution, strongly SVTN-positive ideal solution, SVTN-negative ideal solution and strongly SVTN-negative ideal solution, respectively.

Definition 3.10. Let $\tilde{a}_i = \langle (a_i, b_i, c_i, d_i); w_i, u_i, y_i \rangle \in \Omega$ for all $i = 1, 2$ and \tilde{a}^+ , \tilde{a}_s^+ , \tilde{a}^- and \tilde{a}_s^- be SVTN-positive ideal solution, strongly SVTN-positive ideal solution, SVTN-negative ideal solution and strongly SVTN-negative ideal solution, respectively. Then, the distance between \tilde{a}_i and \tilde{a}^+ , \tilde{a}_s^+ , \tilde{a}^- , \tilde{a}_s^- are denoted as $d_h(\tilde{a}_i, \tilde{a}^+)$, $d_h(\tilde{a}_i, \tilde{a}_s^+)$, $d_h(\tilde{a}_i, \tilde{a}^-)$, $d_h(\tilde{a}_i, \tilde{a}_s^-)$ for all $i = 1, 2$, respectively. Then,

1. If $d_h(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}^+) < d_h(\tilde{a}_2, \tilde{a}^+)$, then \tilde{a}_2 is smaller than \tilde{a}_1 , denoted by $\tilde{a}_1 > \tilde{a}_2$
2. If $d_h(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}^+) = d_h(\tilde{a}_2, \tilde{a}^+)$;
 - (a) If $d_h(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_s^+) < d_h(\tilde{a}_2, \tilde{a}_s^+)$, then \tilde{a}_2 is smaller than \tilde{a}_1 , denoted by $\tilde{a}_1 > \tilde{a}_2$
 - (b) If $d_h(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_s^+) = d_h(\tilde{a}_2, \tilde{a}_s^+)$;
 - i. If $d_h(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}^-) < d_h(\tilde{a}_2, \tilde{a}^-)$, then \tilde{a}_1 is smaller than \tilde{a}_2 , denoted by $\tilde{a}_1 < \tilde{a}_2$
 - ii. If $d_h(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}^-) = d_h(\tilde{a}_2, \tilde{a}^-)$;
 - A. If $d_h(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_s^-) < d_h(\tilde{a}_2, \tilde{a}_s^-)$, then \tilde{a}_1 is smaller than \tilde{a}_2 , denoted by $\tilde{a}_1 < \tilde{a}_2$
 - B. If $d_h(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_s^-) = d_h(\tilde{a}_2, \tilde{a}_s^-)$; \tilde{a}_1 and \tilde{a}_2 are the same, denoted by $\tilde{a}_1 = \tilde{a}_2$

Example 3.11. Assume that $\tilde{a}_1 = \langle (2, 3, 5, 6); 0.3, 0.4, 0.7 \rangle$, $\tilde{a}_2 = \langle (1, 3, 6, 7); 0.7, 0.5, 0.1 \rangle$, $\tilde{a}^+ = \langle (1, 1, 1, 1); 1, 0, 0 \rangle \in \Omega$. Then,

$$\begin{aligned} d_h(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}^+) &= \frac{1}{6} (|(1 + 0.3 - 0.4 - 0.7)2 - |(1 + 1 - 0.0 - 0.0)1| + \\ &\quad |(1 + 0.3 - 0.4 - 0.7)3 - |(1 + 1 - 0.0 - 0.0)1| + \\ &\quad |(1 + 0.3 - 0.4 - 0.7)5 - |(1 + 1 - 0.0 - 0.0)1| + \\ &\quad |(1 + 0.3 - 0.4 - 0.7)6 - |(1 + 1 - 0.0 - 0.0)1|) \\ &= \frac{7}{60} \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} d_h(\tilde{a}_2, \tilde{a}^+) &= \frac{1}{6} (|(1 + 0.7 - 0.5 - 0.1)1 - |(1 + 1 - 0.0 - 0.0)1| + \\ &\quad |(1 + 0.7 - 0.5 - 0.1)3 - |(1 + 1 - 0.0 - 0.0)1| + \\ &\quad |(1 + 0.7 - 0.5 - 0.1)6 - |(1 + 1 - 0.0 - 0.0)1| + \\ &\quad |(1 + 0.7 - 0.5 - 0.1)7 - |(1 + 1 - 0.0 - 0.0)1|) \\ &= \frac{65}{60} \end{aligned}$$

Since $d_h(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}^+) < d_h(\tilde{a}_2, \tilde{a}^+)$, \tilde{a}_2 is smaller than \tilde{a}_1 (or $\tilde{a}_1 > \tilde{a}_2$).

From now on we use $I_n = \{1, 2, \dots, n\}$ $I_m = \{1, 2, \dots, m\}$ and $I_t = \{1, 2, \dots, t\}$ as an index set for $n \in N$, $m \in N$ and $t \in N$, respectively.

4 SVTN-Weighted Operators

In this section, we present some arithmetic and geometric operators including SVTN-weighted geometric operator, SVTN-ordered weighted geometric operator, SVTN-hybrid geometric operator, SVTN-weighted arithmetic operator, SVTN-ordered weighted arithmetic operator and SVTN-hybrid arithmetic operator with their properties.

4.1 SVTN-Weighted Geometric Operators

In this subsection, we introduce some SVTN-weighted geometric operators on the SVTN-numbers.

Definition 4.1. [73] Let $a_{\tilde{j}} = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{a_{\tilde{j}}}, u_{a_{\tilde{j}}}, y_{a_{\tilde{j}}} \rangle \in \Omega$ for all $j \in I_n$. Then, SVTN-weighted geometric operator, denoted by S_{go} , is defined by $S_{go} : \Omega^n \rightarrow \Omega$,

$$S_{go}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \tilde{a}_1^{w_1} \otimes \tilde{a}_2^{w_2} \otimes \dots \otimes \tilde{a}_n^{w_n}$$

where $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is a weight vector of \tilde{a}_j for every $j \in I_n$ such that $w_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$.

Theorem 4.2. [73] Let $a_{\tilde{j}} = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{a_{\tilde{j}}}, u_{a_{\tilde{j}}}, y_{a_{\tilde{j}}} \rangle \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$ and S_{go} be the SVTN-weighted geometric operator. Then, their aggregated value by using $S_{go} : \Omega^n \rightarrow \Omega$, operator is also a SVTN-number and

$$\begin{aligned} S_{go}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) &= \prod_{j=1}^n \tilde{a}_j^{w_j} \\ &= \langle (\prod_{j=1}^n a_j^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n b_j^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n c_j^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n d_j^{w_j}); \\ &\quad \prod_{j=1}^n w_{\tilde{a}_j}^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - u_{\tilde{a}_j})^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - y_{\tilde{a}_j})^{w_j} \rangle \end{aligned}$$

where $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is a weight vector of \tilde{a}_j for all $j \in I_n$ such that $w_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$.

Theorem 4.3. [73] Let $\tilde{a}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{a^-_j}, u_{a^-_j}, y_{a^-_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$. Then,

1. If $\tilde{a}_j = \tilde{a}$, for all $j \in I_n$, then $S_{go}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \tilde{a}$,
2. $\min_{j \in I} \{\tilde{a}_j\} \leq S_{go}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) \leq \max_{j \in I} \{\tilde{a}_j\}$,
3. If $\tilde{a}_j^* = \langle (a_j^*, b_j^*, c_j^*, d_j^*); w_{\tilde{a}_j^*}, u_{\tilde{a}_j^*}, y_{\tilde{a}_j^*} \rangle \in \Omega$ and $\tilde{a}_j \leq \tilde{a}_j^*$ for all $j \in I_n$, then $S_{go}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) \leq S_{go}(\tilde{a}_1^*, \tilde{a}_2^*, \dots, \tilde{a}_n^*)$.

Definition 4.4. Let $\tilde{a}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{\tilde{a}_j}, u_{\tilde{a}_j}, y_{\tilde{a}_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for all $j \in I_n$. Then, an SVTN-ordered weighted geometric operator, denoted by S_{oggo} , is defined by $S_{oggo} : \Omega^n \rightarrow \Omega$,

$$S_{oggo}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \tilde{a}_{\sigma(1)}^{w_1} \otimes \tilde{a}_{\sigma(2)}^{w_2} \otimes \dots \otimes \tilde{a}_{\sigma(n)}^{w_n}$$

where $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is a weight vector of \tilde{a}_j for every $j \in I$ such that $w_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$.

Here, $(\sigma(1), \sigma(2), \dots, \sigma(n))$ is a permutation of $(1, 2, \dots, n)$ such that $a_{\sigma(j-1)} \geq a_{\sigma(j)}$ for all $j \in I_n$.

Theorem 4.5. Let $\tilde{a}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{\tilde{a}_j}, u_{\tilde{a}_j}, y_{\tilde{a}_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$ and S_{oggo} be an SVTN-ordered weighted geometric operator. Then, their aggregated value by using S_{oggo} operator is also a SVTN-number an

$$S_{oggo}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \prod_{j=1}^n \tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}^{w_j} = \langle (\prod_{j=1}^n a_{\sigma(j)}^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n b_{\sigma(j)}^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n c_{\sigma(j)}^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n d_{\sigma(j)}^{w_j}); \prod_{j=1}^n w_{\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}}^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - u_{\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}})^{w_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - y_{\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}})^{w_j} \rangle$$

where $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is a weight vector of \tilde{a}_j for all $j \in I_n$ such that $w_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$.

Theorem 4.6. Let $\tilde{a}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{\tilde{a}_j}, u_{\tilde{a}_j}, y_{\tilde{a}_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$. Then,

1. If $\tilde{a}_j = \tilde{a}$, then $S_{oggo}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \tilde{a}$.
2. $\min_j \{\tilde{a}_j\} \leq S_{oggo}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) \leq \max_j \{\tilde{a}_j\}$
3. If $\tilde{a}_j^* = \langle (a_j^*, b_j^*, c_j^*, d_j^*); w_{\tilde{a}_j^*}, u_{\tilde{a}_j^*}, y_{\tilde{a}_j^*} \rangle \in \Omega$ and $\tilde{a}_j \leq \tilde{a}_j^*$, then $S_{oggo}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) \leq S_{oggo}(\tilde{a}_1^*, \tilde{a}_2^*, \dots, \tilde{a}_n^*)$

4. If $\tilde{a}_j \in \Omega$, then

$$S_{oggo}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = S_{oggo}(\tilde{a}_{\tilde{1}}, \tilde{a}_{\tilde{2}}, \dots, \tilde{a}_{\tilde{n}}) \text{ where } (\tilde{a}_{\tilde{1}}, \tilde{a}_{\tilde{2}}, \dots, \tilde{a}_{\tilde{n}}) \text{ is any permutation of } (\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n).$$

Theorem 4.7. Let $\tilde{a}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{\tilde{a}_j}, u_{\tilde{a}_j}, y_{\tilde{a}_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$ and S_{oggo} be the SVTN-geometric averaging operator. Then, for all $j \in I_n$,

1. If $w = (1, 0, \dots, 0)^T$, then $S_{oggo}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \max_j \{\tilde{a}_j\}$.
2. If $w = (0, 0, \dots, 1)^T$, then $S_{oggo}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \min_j \{\tilde{a}_j\}$.

Definition 4.8. Let $\tilde{a}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{\tilde{a}_j}, u_{\tilde{a}_j}, y_{\tilde{a}_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$. Then, an SVTN-hybrid geometric operator, denoted by $S_{hggo}^{\tilde{s}}$, is defined by

$$S_{hggo}^{\tilde{s}} : \Omega^n \rightarrow \Omega, \quad S_{hggo}^{\tilde{s}}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \tilde{a}_{\sigma(1)}^{\tilde{s}_1} \otimes \tilde{a}_{\sigma(2)}^{\tilde{s}_2} \otimes \dots \otimes \tilde{a}_{\sigma(n)}^{\tilde{s}_n}$$

where for $j \in I_n$, $\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}$ is the j th largest of the weighted SVTN-numbers \tilde{a}_j , $\tilde{a}_j = \tilde{a}_j^{nw_j}$, $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is a weight vector of \tilde{a}_j such that $w_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$, and $\tilde{s} = (\tilde{s}_1, \tilde{s}_2, \dots, \tilde{s}_n)^T$ is a vector associated with the $S_{hggo}^{\tilde{s}}$ such that $\tilde{s}_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{s}_j = 1$.

Theorem 4.9. Let $\tilde{a}_j = ((a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{\tilde{a}_j}, u_{\tilde{a}_j}, y_{\tilde{a}_j}) \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$ and $S_{hgo}^{\tilde{s}}$ be the SVTN-hybrid geometric operator. Then, their aggregated value by using $S_{hgo}^{\tilde{s}}$ operator is also a SVTN-number and

$$S_{hgo}^{\tilde{s}}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \prod_{j=1}^n \tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}^{\tilde{s}_j} = \langle (\prod_{j=1}^n \tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}^{\tilde{s}_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n \tilde{b}_{\sigma(j)}^{\tilde{s}_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n \tilde{c}_{\sigma(j)}^{\tilde{s}_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n \tilde{d}_{\sigma(j)}^{\tilde{s}_j}); \prod_{j=1}^n w_{\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}}^{\tilde{s}_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - u_{\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}})^{\tilde{s}_j}, 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - y_{\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}})^{\tilde{s}_j} \rangle$$

where for $j \in I_n$, $\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}$ is the j th largest of the weighted SVTN-numbers \tilde{a}_j , $\tilde{a}_j = \tilde{a}_j^{nw_j}$, $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is a weight vector of \tilde{a}_j such that $w_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$, and $\tilde{s} = (\tilde{s}_1, \tilde{s}_2, \dots, \tilde{s}_n)^T$ is a vector associated with the $S_{hgo}^{\tilde{s}}$ such that $\tilde{s}_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{s}_j = 1$.

Corollary 4.10. Let $\tilde{a}_j = ((a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{\tilde{a}_j}, u_{\tilde{a}_j}, y_{\tilde{a}_j}) \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$. Then, SVTN-weighted geometric operator S_{go} and SVTN-ordered weighted geometric operator S_{ogo} operator is a special case of the SVTN-hybrid geometric operator $S_{hgo}^{\tilde{s}}$.

4.2 SVTN-Weighted arithmetic Operators

In this subsection, we introduce some SVTN-weighted arithmetic operators on the SVTN-numbers.

Definition 4.11. [73] Let $a^{\sim}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{a^{\sim}_j}, u_{a^{\sim}_j}, y_{a^{\sim}_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for all $j \in I_n$. Then, SVTN-weighted arithmetic operator, denoted by $S_{ao} : \Omega^n \rightarrow \Omega$, is defined by

$$S_{ao}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = w_1 \tilde{a}_1 \oplus w_2 \tilde{a}_2 \oplus \dots \oplus w_n \tilde{a}_n$$

where $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is a weight vector of \tilde{a}_j for every $j \in I_n$ such that $w_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$.

Theorem 4.12. [73] Let $a^{\sim}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{a^{\sim}_j}, u_{a^{\sim}_j}, y_{a^{\sim}_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$ and S_{ao} be the SVTN-weighted arithmetic operator. Then, their aggregated value by using S_{ao} operator is also a SVTN-number and

$$S_{ao}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \tilde{a}_j = \langle (\sum_{j=1}^n w_j a_j, \sum_{j=1}^n w_j b_j, \sum_{j=1}^n w_j c_j, \sum_{j=1}^n w_j d_j); 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - w_{\tilde{a}_j})^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n u_{\tilde{a}_j}^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n y_{\tilde{a}_j}^{w_j} \rangle$$

where $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is a weight vector of a^{\sim}_j for all $j \in I_n$ such that $w_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$.

Theorem 4.13. [73] Let $a^{\sim}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{a^{\sim}_j}, u_{a^{\sim}_j}, y_{a^{\sim}_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$. Then,

1. If $\tilde{a}_j = \tilde{a}$, for all $j \in I_n$, then $S_{ao}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \tilde{a}$,
2. $\min_j \{\tilde{a}_j\} \leq S_{ao}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) \leq \max_j \{\tilde{a}_j\}$,
3. If $\tilde{a}_j^* = \langle (a_j^*, b_j^*, c_j^*, d_j^*); w_{\tilde{a}_j^*}, u_{\tilde{a}_j^*}, y_{\tilde{a}_j^*} \rangle \in \Omega$ and $\tilde{a}_j \leq \tilde{a}_j^*$ for all $j \in I_n$, then $S_{ao}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) \leq S_{ao}(\tilde{a}_1^*, \tilde{a}_2^*, \dots, \tilde{a}_n^*)$.

Definition 4.14. Let $\tilde{a}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{\tilde{a}_j}, u_{\tilde{a}_j}, y_{\tilde{a}_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for all $j \in I_n$. Then, an SVTN-ordered weighted arithmetic operator, denoted by $S_{oao} : \Omega^n \rightarrow \Omega$, is defined by

$$S_{oao}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = w_1 \tilde{a}_{\sigma(1)} \oplus w_2 \tilde{a}_{\sigma(2)} \oplus \dots \oplus w_n \tilde{a}_{\sigma(n)}$$

where $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is a weight vector of \tilde{a}_j for every $j \in I$ such that $w_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$.

Here, $(\sigma(1), \sigma(2), \dots, \sigma(n))$ is a permutation of $(1, 2, \dots, n)$ such that $a_{\sigma(j-1)} \geq a_{\sigma(j)}$ for all $j \in I_n$.

Theorem 4.15. Let $\tilde{a}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{\tilde{a}_j}, u_{\tilde{a}_j}, y_{\tilde{a}_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$ and S_{oao} be an SVTN-ordered weighted arithmetic operator. Then, their aggregated value by using S_{oao} operator is also a SVTN-number and

$$S_{oao}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \sum_{j=1}^n w_j \tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)} = \langle (\sum_{j=1}^n w_j a_{\sigma(j)}, \sum_{j=1}^n w_j b_{\sigma(j)}, \sum_{j=1}^n w_j c_{\sigma(j)}, \sum_{j=1}^n w_j d_{\sigma(j)}); 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - w_{\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}})^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n u_{\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}}^{w_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n y_{\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}}^{w_j} \rangle$$

where $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is a weight vector of \tilde{a}_j for all $j \in I_n$ such that $w_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$.

Theorem 4.16. Let $\tilde{a}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{\tilde{a}_j}, u_{\tilde{a}_j}, y_{\tilde{a}_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$ and S_{oao} be the SVTN-arithmetic averaging operator. Then, for all $j \in I_n$,

1. If $\tilde{a}_j = \tilde{a}$, then $S_{oao}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \tilde{a}$.
2. $\min_j \{\tilde{a}_j\} \leq S_{oao}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) \leq \max_j \{\tilde{a}_j\}$
3. If $\tilde{a}_j^* = \langle (a_j^*, b_j^*, c_j^*, d_j^*); w_{\tilde{a}_j^*}, u_{\tilde{a}_j^*}, y_{\tilde{a}_j^*} \rangle \in \Omega$ and $\tilde{a}_j \leq \tilde{a}_j^*$, then $S_{oao}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) \leq S_{oao}(\tilde{a}_1^*, \tilde{a}_2^*, \dots, \tilde{a}_n^*)$
4. If $\tilde{a}_j \in \Omega$, then $S_{oao}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = S_{oao}(\tilde{a}_{\sigma(1)}, \tilde{a}_{\sigma(2)}, \dots, \tilde{a}_{\sigma(n)})$ where $(\tilde{a}_{\sigma(1)}, \tilde{a}_{\sigma(2)}, \dots, \tilde{a}_{\sigma(n)})$ is any permutation of $(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n)$.

Theorem 4.17. Let $\tilde{a}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{\tilde{a}_j}, u_{\tilde{a}_j}, y_{\tilde{a}_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$ and S_{oao} be the SVTN-arithmetic averaging operator. Then, for all $j \in I_n$,

1. If $w = (1, 0, \dots, 0)^T$, then $S_{oao}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \max_j \{\tilde{a}_j\}$.
2. If $w = (0, 0, \dots, 1)^T$, then $S_{oao}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \min_j \{\tilde{a}_j\}$.

Definition 4.18. Let $\tilde{a}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{\tilde{a}_j}, u_{\tilde{a}_j}, y_{\tilde{a}_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$. Then, an SVTN-hybrid arithmetic operator, denoted by $S_{hao}^{\tilde{s}} : \Omega^n \rightarrow \Omega$, is defined by

$$S_{hao}^{\tilde{s}}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \tilde{s}_1 \tilde{a}_{\sigma(1)} \oplus \tilde{s}_2 \tilde{a}_{\sigma(2)} \oplus \dots \oplus \tilde{s}_n \tilde{a}_{\sigma(n)}$$

where for $j \in I_n$, $\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}$ is the j th largest of the weighted SVTN-numbers \tilde{a}_j , $\tilde{a}_j = \tilde{a}_j^{nw_j}$, $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is a weight vector of \tilde{a}_j such that $w_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$, and $\tilde{s} = (\tilde{s}_1, \tilde{s}_2, \dots, \tilde{s}_n)^T$ is a vector associated with the $S_{hao}^{\tilde{s}}$ such that $\tilde{s}_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{s}_j = 1$.

Theorem 4.19. Let $\tilde{a}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{\tilde{a}_j}, u_{\tilde{a}_j}, y_{\tilde{a}_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$ and $S_{hao}^{\tilde{s}}$ be the SVTN-hybrid arithmetic operator. Then, their aggregated value by using $S_{hao}^{\tilde{s}}$ operator is also a SVTN-number and

$$S_{hao}^{\tilde{s}}(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_2, \dots, \tilde{a}_n) = \sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)} \tilde{s}_j = \langle (\sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}^{\tilde{s}_j}, \sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{b}_{\sigma(j)}^{\tilde{s}_j}, \sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{c}_{\sigma(j)}^{\tilde{s}_j}, \sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{d}_{\sigma(j)}^{\tilde{s}_j}); 1 - \prod_{j=1}^n (1 - w_{\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}}^{\tilde{s}_j}), \prod_{j=1}^n u_{\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}}^{\tilde{s}_j}, \prod_{j=1}^n y_{\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}}^{\tilde{s}_j} \rangle$$

where for $j \in I_n$, $\tilde{a}_{\sigma(j)}$ is the j th largest of the weighted SVTN-numbers \tilde{a}_j , $\tilde{a}_j = \tilde{a}_j^{nw_j}$, $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n)^T$ is a weight vector of \tilde{a}_j such that $w_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n w_j = 1$, and $\tilde{s} = (\tilde{s}_1, \tilde{s}_2, \dots, \tilde{s}_n)^T$ is a vector associated with the $S_{hao}^{\tilde{s}}$ such that $\tilde{s}_j \in [0, 1]$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{s}_j = 1$.

Corollary 4.20. Let $\tilde{a}_j = \langle (a_j, b_j, c_j, d_j); w_{\tilde{a}_j}, u_{\tilde{a}_j}, y_{\tilde{a}_j} \rangle \in \Omega$ for $j \in I_n$. Then, SVTN-weighted arithmetic operator S_{ao} and SVTN-weighted arithmetic operator S_{oao} operator is a special case of the SVTN-hybrid arithmetic operator $S_{hao}^{\tilde{s}}$.

5 SVTN-Group Decision Making Method

In this section, by using the $S_{hgo}^{\tilde{s}}$ and S_{go} operators we define a multi attribute group decision making method called SVTN-group decision making method.

Definition 5.1. Let $B = \{B_1, B_2, \dots, B_m\}$ be a set of alternatives, $U = \{u_1, u_2, \dots, u_n\}$ be a set of attributes, $D = \{d_1, d_2, \dots, d_t\}$ be a set of decision makers, $\tilde{s} = (\tilde{s}_1, \tilde{s}_2, \dots, \tilde{s}_n)^T$ be a weighting vector of the attributes where $\tilde{s}_j \in [0, 1]$ for $j \in I_n$ and $\sum_{j=1}^n \tilde{s}_j = 1$, and $w = (w_1, w_2, \dots, w_t)^T$ be a weighting vector of the decision makers such that $w_j \in [0, 1]$ for $j \in I_n$ and $\sum_{j=1}^t w_j = 1$. If $\tilde{a}_{ij}^k = \langle (a_{ij}^k, b_{ij}^k, c_{ij}^k, d_{ij}^k); w_{ij}^k, u_{ij}^k, y_{ij}^k \rangle \in \Omega$, then

$$[\tilde{a}_{ij}^k]_{m \times n} = \begin{matrix} & u_1 & u_2 & \dots & u_n \\ B_1 & \left(\begin{matrix} \tilde{a}_{11}^k & \tilde{a}_{12}^k & \dots & \tilde{a}_{1n}^k \\ \tilde{a}_{21}^k & \tilde{a}_{22}^k & \dots & \tilde{a}_{2n}^k \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \tilde{a}_{m1}^k & \tilde{a}_{m2}^k & \dots & \tilde{a}_{mn}^k \end{matrix} \right) \end{matrix}$$

is called an SVTN-group decision making matrix of the decision maker d_k for each $k \in I_t$. The matrix is also written shortly as

$$[\tilde{a}_{ij}^k]_{m \times n} = \langle (a_{ij}^k, b_{ij}^k, c_{ij}^k, d_{ij}^k); w_{ij}^k, u_{ij}^k, y_{ij}^k \rangle$$

Now, we can give an algorithm of the SVTN-group decision making method as follows;

Algorithm:

Step 1. Construct

$[\tilde{a}_{ij}^k]_{m \times n} = \langle (a_{ij}^k, b_{ij}^k, c_{ij}^k, d_{ij}^k); w_{ij}^k, u_{ij}^k, y_{ij}^k \rangle$ of d_k for each $k \in I_t$.

Step 2. Compute $\tilde{a}_i^k = S_{go}(\tilde{a}_{i1}^k, \tilde{a}_{i2}^k, \dots, \tilde{a}_{in}^k) = \prod_{j=1}^n (\tilde{a}_{ij}^k)^{w_j}$ for each $k \in I_t$ and $i \in I_m$ to derive the individual overall preference SVTN-values \tilde{a}_i^k of the alternative B_i .

Step 3. Compute $\tilde{a}_i = S_{hgo}^{\tilde{s}}(\tilde{a}_i^1, \tilde{a}_i^2, \dots, \tilde{a}_i^t) = \langle (a_i, b_i, c_i); w_{\tilde{a}_i}, u_{\tilde{a}_i}, y_{\tilde{a}_i} \rangle$ for each $i \in I_m$ to derive the collective overall preference SVTN-values \tilde{a}_i of the alternative B_i .

Step 4. Compute $d_h(\tilde{a}_i, \tilde{a}^+)$ for each $i \in I_m$.

Step 5. Rank all alternatives B_i according to the $d_h(\tilde{a}_i, \tilde{a}^+)$ for each $i \in I_m$.

Example 5.2. (It's adopted from [70]) Let us suppose there is a risk investment company, which wants to invest a sum of money in the best option. There is a panel with five possible alternatives (engineer construction projects) to invest the money. The risk investment company must take a decision according to four attributes: $u_1 =$ "risk analysis", $u_2 =$ "growth analysis", $u_3 =$ "social-political impact analysis", $u_4 =$ "environmental impact analysis". The five possible alternatives B_i ($i = 1, 2, \dots, 5$) are to be evaluated using the SVTN-numbers by the four decision makers (whose weighting vector $w = (0.2, 0.4, 0.1, 0.3)^T$) under the above four attributes (whose weighting vector $\tilde{s} = (0.25, 0.25, 0.25, 0.25)^T$), and construct, respectively,

Step 1. For each $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$, the decision maker d_k construct own decision matrices $[\tilde{a}_{ij}^k]_{5 \times 4}$ as Table 1:

Step 2. For each $k = 1, 2, 3, 4$ and $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ compute $\tilde{a}_i^k = S_{go}(\tilde{a}_{i1}^k, \tilde{a}_{i2}^k, \dots, \tilde{a}_{in}^k)$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{a}_1^1 &= ((0.170, 0.411, 0.606, 0.814); 0.442, 0.749, 0.409) \\ \tilde{a}_2^1 &= ((0.194, 0.342, 0.517, 0.800); 0.534, 0.543, 0.302) \\ \tilde{a}_3^1 &= ((0.224, 0.259, 0.517, 0.628); 0.237, 0.513, 0.281) \\ \tilde{a}_4^1 &= ((0.214, 0.332, 0.464, 0.774); 0.460, 0.518, 0.407) \\ \tilde{a}_5^1 &= ((0.139, 0.209, 0.401, 0.580); 0.186, 0.587, 0.332) \\ \tilde{a}_1^2 &= ((0.226, 0.278, 0.459, 0.763); 0.540, 0.423, 0.500) \\ \tilde{a}_2^2 &= ((0.285, 0.388, 0.592, 0.728); 0.379, 0.686, 0.522) \\ \tilde{a}_3^2 &= ((0.476, 0.581, 0.700, 0.814); 0.394, 0.349, 0.300) \\ \tilde{a}_4^2 &= ((0.230, 0.332, 0.613, 0.738); 0.564, 0.714, 0.346) \\ \tilde{a}_5^2 &= ((0.132, 0.147, 0.355, 0.531); 0.293, 0.396, 0.635) \\ \tilde{a}_1^3 &= ((0.115, 0.155, 0.459, 0.599); 0.275, 0.806, 0.674) \\ \tilde{a}_2^3 &= ((0.298, 0.375, 0.592, 0.806); 0.309, 0.387, 0.679) \\ \tilde{a}_3^3 &= ((0.107, 0.112, 0.150, 0.513); 0.491, 0.537, 0.670) \\ \tilde{a}_4^3 &= ((0.200, 0.310, 0.565, 0.673); 0.500, 0.346, 0.693) \\ \tilde{a}_5^3 &= ((0.164, 0.176, 0.355, 0.650); 0.426, 0.527, 0.519) \\ \tilde{a}_1^4 &= ((0.182, 0.302, 0.537, 0.781); 0.275, 0.627, 0.527) \\ \tilde{a}_2^4 &= ((0.154, 0.305, 0.428, 0.693); 0.225, 0.568, 0.617) \\ \tilde{a}_3^4 &= ((0.000, 0.232, 0.504, 0.675); 0.354, 0.551, 0.513) \\ \tilde{a}_4^4 &= ((0.200, 0.300, 0.417, 0.660); 0.509, 0.481, 0.342) \\ \tilde{a}_5^4 &= ((0.000, 0.182, 0.374, 0.625); 0.282, 0.424, 0.270) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{a}_1^1 &= ((0.170, 0.411, 0.606, 0.814); 0.442, 0.749, 0.409) \\ \tilde{a}_2^1 &= ((0.194, 0.342, 0.517, 0.800); 0.534, 0.543, 0.302) \\ \tilde{a}_3^1 &= ((0.224, 0.259, 0.517, 0.628); 0.237, 0.513, 0.281) \\ \tilde{a}_4^1 &= ((0.214, 0.332, 0.464, 0.774); 0.460, 0.518, 0.407) \\ \tilde{a}_5^1 &= ((0.139, 0.209, 0.401, 0.580); 0.186, 0.587, 0.332) \\ \tilde{a}_1^2 &= ((0.226, 0.278, 0.459, 0.763); 0.540, 0.423, 0.500) \\ \tilde{a}_2^2 &= ((0.285, 0.388, 0.592, 0.728); 0.379, 0.686, 0.522) \\ \tilde{a}_3^2 &= ((0.476, 0.581, 0.700, 0.814); 0.394, 0.349, 0.300) \\ \tilde{a}_4^2 &= ((0.230, 0.332, 0.613, 0.738); 0.564, 0.714, 0.346) \\ \tilde{a}_5^2 &= ((0.132, 0.147, 0.355, 0.531); 0.293, 0.396, 0.635) \\ \tilde{a}_1^3 &= ((0.115, 0.155, 0.459, 0.599); 0.275, 0.806, 0.674) \\ \tilde{a}_2^3 &= ((0.298, 0.375, 0.592, 0.806); 0.309, 0.387, 0.679) \\ \tilde{a}_3^3 &= ((0.107, 0.112, 0.150, 0.513); 0.491, 0.537, 0.670) \\ \tilde{a}_4^3 &= ((0.200, 0.310, 0.565, 0.673); 0.500, 0.346, 0.693) \\ \tilde{a}_5^3 &= ((0.164, 0.176, 0.355, 0.650); 0.426, 0.527, 0.519) \\ \tilde{a}_1^4 &= ((0.182, 0.302, 0.537, 0.781); 0.275, 0.627, 0.527) \\ \tilde{a}_2^4 &= ((0.154, 0.305, 0.428, 0.693); 0.225, 0.568, 0.617) \\ \tilde{a}_3^4 &= ((0.000, 0.232, 0.504, 0.675); 0.354, 0.551, 0.513) \\ \tilde{a}_4^4 &= ((0.200, 0.300, 0.417, 0.660); 0.509, 0.481, 0.342) \\ \tilde{a}_5^4 &= ((0.000, 0.182, 0.374, 0.625); 0.282, 0.424, 0.270) \end{aligned}$$

Step 3. Assume that $w = (0.2, 0.4, 0.1, 0.3)^T$ and $\tilde{s} = (0.25, 0.25, 0.25)^T$. We can compute

$$\tilde{a}_i = S_{hgo}^{\tilde{s}}(\tilde{a}_i^1, \tilde{a}_i^2, \dots, \tilde{a}_i^t) = \langle (a_i, b_i, c_i); w_{\tilde{a}_i}, u_{\tilde{a}_i}, y_{\tilde{a}_i} \rangle$$

for each $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \tilde{a}_1 &= ((0.187, 0.291, 0.509, 0.760); 0.396, 0.569, 0.513) \\ \tilde{a}_2 &= ((0.219, 0.351, 0.523, 0.738); 0.340, 0.584, 0.536) \\ \tilde{a}_3 &= ((0.000, 0.298, 0.524, 0.698); 0.352, 0.451, 0.414) \\ \tilde{a}_4 &= ((0.214, 0.320, 0.512, 0.714); 0.519, 0.553, 0.404) \\ \tilde{a}_5 &= ((0.000, 0.171, 0.370, 0.579); 0.274, 0.450, 0.479) \end{aligned}$$

Step 4. Compute $d_h(\tilde{a}_i, \tilde{a}_i^+)$ for each alternative $B_i, i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$, as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} d_h(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_1^+) &= 1.242, d_h(\tilde{a}_2, \tilde{a}_2^+) = 1.266, \\ d_h(\tilde{a}_3, \tilde{a}_3^+) &= 1.210, d_h(\tilde{a}_4, \tilde{a}_4^+) = 1.169, \\ d_h(\tilde{a}_5, \tilde{a}_5^+) &= 1.269 \end{aligned}$$

Then we get the rank,

$$d_h(\tilde{a}_5, \tilde{a}_5^+) > d_h(\tilde{a}_2, \tilde{a}_2^+) > d_h(\tilde{a}_1, \tilde{a}_1^+) > d_h(\tilde{a}_3, \tilde{a}_3^+) > d_h(\tilde{a}_4, \tilde{a}_4^+)$$

Step 5. Therefore, we can rank all alternatives B_i according to the $d_h(\tilde{a}_i, \tilde{a}_i^+)$ for each $i = 1, 2, 3, 4, 5$.

$$B_5 < B_2 < B_1 < B_3 < B_4$$

and thus the most desirable alternative is B_4 .

6 Comparative Analysis and Discussion

In this section, a comparative study is presented to show the flexibility and feasibility of the introduced SVTN-group decision making method. Different methods used to solve the same SVTN-group decision making problem with SVTN-information is given by Ye [73]. The ranking results obtained by different methods are summarized in Table 2.

From the results presented in Table 2, the best alternative in proposed method and Ye’s method [73] with geometric operator is B_4 , whilst the worst one is B_5 . In contrast, by using the methods in the proposed method and Ye’s method [73] with arithmetic operator, the best is B_3 , whilst the worst is B_5 . There are a number of reasons why differences exist between the final rankings of the methods. First, the author uses a score and accurate function in Ye’s method [73] with arithmetic operator and Ye’s method [73] with geometric operator. Moreover, different aggregation operators, which is arithmetic and geometric operator, lead to different rankings because the operators emphasize the decision makers judgments differently. The proposed method is different in that it contains two major phrases. First, the proposed method uses both SVTN-weighted geo-metric operator and the SVTN-hybrid geometric operator to aggregate the SVTN-numbers. Second, based on distance measure, the method uses SVTN-positive ideal solution and SVTN-negative ideal solution to rank the SVTN-information. Finally, the ranking of the proposed method is similar to other methods. Therefore, the proposed method is flexible and feasible.

7 Conclusion

Due to the ambiguity of people's thinking and the complexity of objective things, the attribute values of the MAGDM problems cannot always be expressed by exact and crisp values and it may be easier to describe them by neutrosophic information. This paper introduced an MAGDM in which the attribute values are expressed with the SVTN-numbers, which are solved by developing a new decision method based on geometric aggregation operators of SVTN-numbers. The proposed method with SVTN-numbers is more suitable for real scientific and engineering applications, because the proposed decision-making method includes much more information and can deal with indeterminate and inconsistent decision-making problems. In the future, we shall further develop more aggregation operators for SVTN-numbers and apply them to solve practical applications in areas such as group decision making, expert system, information fusion system, fault diagnoses, medical diagnoses and so on.

References

- [1] A. Q. Ansaria, R. Biswas and S. Aggarwal, Neutrosophic classifier: An extension of fuzzy classifier, *Applied Soft Computing* 13 (2013) 563–573.
- [2] C. Ashbacher, *Introduction to Neutrosophic Logic*, American Research Press Rehoboth 2002.
- [3] K. Atanassov, Intuitionistic fuzzy sets, *Fuzzy Sets and Systems*, 20 (1986) 87-96.
- [4] K. Atanassov and G. Garov, Interval valued intuitionistic fuzzy sets, *Fuzzy Sets and Systems* 31 (1989) 343-349.
- [5] S. Broumi, M. Talea, F. Smarandache and A. Bakali, Single Valued Neutrosophic Graphs: Degree, Order and Size, *IEEE International Conference on Fuzzy Systems (FUZZ)*, (2016) 2444-2451.
- [6] S. Broumi, A. Bakali, M. Talea, F. Smarandache and L. Vladareanu, Computation of Shortest Path Problem in a Network with SV-Trapezoidal Neutrosophic Numbers, *Proceedings of the 2016 International Conference on Advanced Mechatronic Systems*, Melbourne, Australia, (2016) 417-422.
- [7] S. Broumi, A. Bakali, M. Talea, F. Smarandache and L. Vladareanu, Applying Dijkstra Algorithm for Solving Neutrosophic Shortest Path Problem, *Proceedings of the 2016 International Conference on Advanced Mechatronic Systems*, Melbourne, Australia, (2016) 412-416.
- [8] Biswas, P., Pramanik, S., and Giri, B. C. Neutrosophic TOPSIS with Group Decision Making, (2019) 543-585.
- [9] P. Biswas, S. Pramanik, and B. C. Giri., TOPSIS strategy for multi-attribute decision making with trapezoidal neutrosophic numbers, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 19 (2018), 29-39.
- [10] P. Biswas, S. Pramanik, and B. C. Giri., Distance measure based MADM strategy with interval trapezoidal neutrosophic numbers, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 19 (2018), 40-46.
- [11] P. Biswas, S. Pramanik, and B. C. Giri., Entropy based grey relational analysis method for multi-attribute decision making under single valued neutrosophic assessments, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 2 (2014), 102-110.
- [12] P. Biswas, S. Pramanik, and B. C. Giri., A new methodology for neutrosophic multi-attribute decision making with unknown weight information, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 3 (2014), 42-52.
- [13] P. Biswas, S. Pramanik, and B. C. Giri., Aggregation of triangular fuzzy neutrosophic set information and its application to multi-attribute decision making, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 12 (2016), 20-40.

- [14] P. Biswas, S. Pramanik, and B. C. Giri., Value and ambiguity index based ranking method of single-valued trapezoidal neutrosophic numbers and its application to multi-attribute decision making, *Neutrosophic Sets and Systems*, 12 (2016), 127-138.
- [15] P. Biswas, S. Pramanik, and B. C. Giri., Multi-attribute group decision making based on expected value of neutrosophic trapezoidal numbers, *New trends in neutrosophic theory and applications-Vol-II*, Pons Editions, Brussels (2018), (pp. 103-124).
- [16] T.Y. Chen, H.P. Wang, Y.Y. Lu, A multicriteria group decision-making approach based on interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy sets: a comparative perspective, *Exp. Syst. Appl.* 38 (6) (2011) 7647-7658.
- [17] Y. Chen, B. Li, Dynamic multi-attribute decision making model based on triangular intuitionistic fuzzy numbers, *Scientia Iranica B* (2011) 18 (2), 268-274.
- [18] S. Das, D. Guha, Ranking of Intuitionistic Fuzzy Number by Centroid Point, *Journal of Industrial and Intelligent Information* 1/2 (2013) 107–110.
- [19] N. Çağman, I. Deli, Means of FP-Soft Sets and its Applications, *Hacettepe Journal of Mathematics and Statistics*, 41/5 (2012) 615–625.
- [20] N. Çağman, I. Deli, Product of FP-Soft Sets and its Applications, *Hacettepe Journal of Mathematics and Statistics* 41/3 (2012) 365 -374.
- [21] I. Deli, Y. Subas, Single valued neutrosophic numbers and their applications to multicriteria decision making problem, (2014) viXra preprint viXra:1412.0012.
- [22] I. Deli, Y. Şubaş, A ranking method of single valued neutrosophic numbers and its applications to multiattribute decision making problems, *International Journal of Machine Learning and Cybernetics*, DOI: 10.1007/s13042-016-0505-3.
- [23] D. Dubois, F. H. Prade, Operations on fuzzy numbers, *International Journal of Systems Sciences* 9/6 (1978) 613-626.
- [24] M. Esmailzadeh, M. Esmailzadeh, New distance between triangular intuitionistic fuzzy numbers, *Advances in Computational Mathematics and its Applications* 2/3 (2013) 310–314.
- [25] B. Farhadinia, Adrian I. Ban, Developing new similarity measures of generalized intuitionistic fuzzy numbers and generalized interval-valued fuzzy numbers from similarity measures of generalized fuzzy numbers, *Mathematical and Computer Modelling* 57 (2013) 812-825.
- [26] D. F.Li, *Decision and Game Theory in Management With Intuitionistic Fuzzy Sets Studies in Fuzziness and Soft Computing* Volume 308, springer, 2014.
- [27] A. N. Gani, N. Sritharan C. Arun Kumar, Weighted Average Rating (WAR) Method for Solving Group Decision Making Problem Using an Intuitionistic Trapezoidal Fuzzy Hybrid Aggregation Operator, *International Journal of Pure and Applied Sciences and Technology Int. J. Pure Appl. Sci. Technol.*, 6(1) (2011) 54–61.
- [28] H. Garg, Nancy, Linguistic single valued neutrosophic prioritized aggregation operators and their applications to multiple attribute group decision making, *Journal of Ambient Intelligence and Humanized Computing*, Springer, 2018, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12652-018-0723-5>.
- [29] H. Garg, Nancy, Non-linear programming method for multi-criteria decision making problems under interval neutrosophic set environment, *Applied Intelligence* <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10489-017-1070-5> .
- [30] H. Garg, Nancy, Some New Biparametric Distance Measures on Single-Valued Neutrosophic Sets with Applications to Pattern Recognition and Medical Diagnosis, *Information*, 2017, 8(4), 162; doi:10.3390/info8040162.
- [31] W. Jianqiang, Z. Zhong, Aggregation operators on intuitionistic trapezoidal fuzzy number and its application to multi-criteria decision making problems, *Journal of Systems Engineering and Electronics*, 20/2 (2009) 321-326.

- [32] C. Kahraman and I. Otay (eds.), Fuzzy Multi-criteria Decision-Making Using Neutrosophic Sets, Studies in Fuzziness and Soft Computing 369, Springer Nature Switzerland AG, (2019).
- [33] D. F. Li, A ratio ranking method of triangular intuitionistic fuzzy numbers and its application to MADM problems, Computers and Mathematics with Applications 60 (2010) 1557–1570
- [34] G.S. Mahapatra, T.K. Roy, Intuitionistic Fuzzy Number and Its Arithmetic Operation with Application on System Failure, Journal of Uncertain Systems 7/2 (2013) 92–107.
- [35] K. Mondal, S. Pramanik, and B. C. Giri. Single valued neutrosophic hyperbolic sine similarity measure based MADM strategy. Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, 20 (2018), 3-11. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1235383>.
- [36] K. Mondal, S. Pramanik, and B. C. Giri., Hybrid binary logarithm similarity measure for MAGDM problems under SVNS assessments. Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, 20 (2018), 12-25. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1235365>.
- [37] K. Mondal, S. Pramanik, and B. C. Giri., Interval neutrosophic tangent similarity measure based MADM strategy and its application to MADM problems. Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, 19 (2018), 47-56. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1235201>
- [38] K. Mondal, and S. Pramanik, Multi-criteria group decision making approach for teacher recruitment in higher education under simplified Neutrosophic environment. Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, 6 (2014), 28-34.
- [39] K. Mondal, and S. Pramanik, Neutrosophic decision making model of school choice. Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, 7 (2015), 62-68.
- [40] K. Mondal, and S. Pramanik, Neutrosophic tangent similarity measure and its application to multiple attribute decision making, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, 9, (2015) 80-87.
- [41] H. M. Nehi, A New Ranking Method for Intuitionistic Fuzzy Numbers, International Journal of Fuzzy Systems, 12/1 (2010) 80–86.
- [42] M. Palanivelrajan and K. Kaliraju, A Study on Intuitionistic Fuzzy Number Group, International Journal of Fuzzy Mathematics and Systems. 2/3 (2012) 269–277.
- [43] Z. Pawlak, Rough sets, International Journal of Information and Computer Sciences, 11 (1982) 341-356.
- [44] S. Pramanik, S. Dalapati, S. Alam, S. Smarandache, and T. K. Roy, NS-cross entropy based MAGDM under single valued neutrosophic set environment, Information, (2018) doi:10.3390/info9020037.
- [45] S. Pramanik, S. Dalapati, S. Alam, S. Smarandache, and T. K. Roy, IN-cross entropy based MAGDM strategy under interval neutrosophic set environment, Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, 18, (2017) 43-57. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1175162>.
- [46] S. Pramanik, R. Mallick, and A. Dasgupta, Contributions of selected Indian researchers to multi-attribute decision making in neutrosophic environment. Neutrosophic Sets and Systems, 20 (2018), 108-131. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1284870>.
- [47] S. Pramanik, P. Biswas, P., and B. C. Giri., Hybrid vector similarity measures and their applications to multi-attribute decision making under neutrosophic environment. Neural Computing and Applications, 28 (5)(2017), 1163-1176. DOI 10.1007/s00521-015-2125-3.
- [48] J.-j. Peng, J.-q. Wang, J. Wang, H.-y. Zhang, X.-h. Chen, Simplified neutrosophic sets and their applications in multi-criteria group decision-making problems, International Journal of Systems Science, DOI:10.1080/00207721.2014.994050, 2015.
- [49] J.-j. Peng, J.-Q. Wang, X.-H. Wu, J. Wang and X.-h. Chen, Multi-valued Neutrosophic Sets and Power Aggregation Operators with Their Applications in Multi-criteria Group Decision- making Problems, International Journal of Computational Intelligence Systems, 8(4):345-363, 2015.
- [50] J. Peng, J. Wang, H. Zhang, X. Chen. An outranking approach for multi-criteria decision-making problems with simplified neutrosophic sets, Applied Soft Computing, 25, (2014) 336-346.

- [51] S. S. Roseline, E. C. Henry Amirtharaj, A New Method for Ranking of Intuitionistic Fuzzy Numbers, *Indian Journal of Applied Research*, 3/6 (2013).
- [52] A. A. Salama, S. A. Alblowi, Neutrosophic Set and Neutrosophic Topological Spaces, *IOSR Journal of Mathematics*, 3/4 (2012) 31–35.
- [53] F. Smarandache, Neutrosophy and Neutrosophic Logic, First International Conference on Neutrosophy, Neutrosophic Logic, Set, Probability, and Statistics University of New Mexico, Gallup, NM 87301, USA, 2002.
- [54] F.Smarandache, "A Unifying Field in Logics. Neutrosophy: Neutrosophic Probability, Set and Logic". Rehoboth: American Research Press, 1998.
- [55] F. Smarandache, Neutrosophic set, a generalisation of the intuitionistic fuzzy sets, *Int. J. Pure Appl. Math.* 24 (2005) 287-297.
- [56] Y. Şubaş (2015) Neutrosophic numbers and their application to Multi-attribute decision making problems. (In Turkish) (Masters Thesis, 7 Aralık University, Graduate School of Natural and Applied Science)
- [57] Y.X. Ma, J.Q. Wang, J. Wang, X.H. Wu, An interval neutrosophic linguistic multi-criteria group decision-making method and its application in selecting medical treatment options, *Neural Computing and Applications*, DOI: 10.1007/s00521-016-2203-1, 2016
- [58] Z.P. Tian, H.Y. Zhang, J. Wang, J.Q. Wang, X.H. Chen, Multi-criteria decision-making method based on a cross-entropy with interval neutrosophic sets, *International Journal of Systems Science*, DOI: 10.1080/00207721.2015.1102359.
- [59] Z.S. Xu, Intuitionistic fuzzy aggregation operators, *IEEE Trans. Fuzzy Syst.* 15 (6) (2007) 1179-1187.
- [60] Z.Xu, R. R. Yager, Some geometric aggregation operators based on intuitionistic fuzzy sets, *International Journal of General Systems*, 35(4) (2006), 417433.
- [61] J. Wang, R. Nie, H. Zhang, X. Chen, New operators on triangular intuitionistic fuzzy numbers and their applications in system fault analysis, *Information Sciences* 251 (2013) 79-95.
- [62] H. Wang, F. Smarandache, Y.Q. Zhang, R. Sunderraman, *Interval Neutrosophic Sets and Logic: Theory and Applications in Computing*, Hexis; Neutrosophic book series, No: 5, 2005.
- [63] H. Wang, F. Y. Smarandache, Q. Zhang, R. Sunderraman, Single valued neutrosophic sets, *Multispace and Multistructure* 4 (2010) 410–413.
- [64] S. P. Wan, Power average operators of trapezoidal intuitionistic fuzzy numbers and application to multi-attribute group decision making, *Applied Mathematical Modelling* 37 (2013) 4112-4126.
- [65] S. P. Wan, Q. Y. Wanga, J. Y. Dong, The extended VIKOR method for multi-attribute group decision making with triangular intuitionistic fuzzy numbers, *Knowledge-Based Systems* 52 (2013) 65-77.
- [66] G. Wei, Some Arithmetic Aggregation Operators with Intuitionistic Trapezoidal Fuzzy Numbers and Their Application to Group Decision Making, *Journal of Computers*, 5/3 (2010) 345–351.
- [67] G. Wei, Some induced geometric aggregation operators with intuitionistic fuzzy information and their application to group decision making, *Applied Soft Computing* 10 (2010) 423-431.
- [68] J. Wu, Q. Cao, Same families of geometric aggregation operators with intuitionistic trapezoidal fuzzy numbers, *Applied Mathematical Modelling* 37 (2013) 318-327.
- [69] J. Wu, Y. liu, An approach for multiple attribute group decision making problems with interval-valued intuitionistic trapezoidal fuzzy numbers, *Computers and Industrial Engineering* 66 (2013) 311-324.
- [70] J. Ye, Trapezoidal neutrosophic set and its application to multiple attribute decision-making, *Neural Comput. and Appl.*, DOI:10.1007/s00521-014-1787-6

- [71] F. Ye, An extended TOPSIS method with interval-valued intuitionistic fuzzy numbers for virtual enterprise partner selection, *Expert Systems with Applications*, *Expert Systems with Applications* 37 (2010) 7050-7055.
- [72] J. Ye, Expected value method for intuitionistic trapezoidal fuzzy multicriteria decision-making problems, *Expert Systems with Applications* 38 (2011) 11730-11734.
- [73] J. Ye, Some Weighted Aggregation Operators of Trapezoidal Neutrosophic Numbers and Their Multiple Attribute Decision Making Method, (2016) (also, accepted in *Informatica*) <http://vixra.org/abs/1508.0403>.
- [74] J. Ye, Trapezoidal neutrosophic set and its application to multiple attribute decision-making, *Neural Comput. and Applic.*, 26 (2015) 1157-1166.
- [75] D. Yu, Intuitionistic Trapezoidal Fuzzy Information Aggregation Methods and Their Applications to Teaching Quality Evaluation, *Journal of Information Computational Science* 10/6 (2013) 1861–1869.
- [76] Z. Yue, Aggregating crisp values into intuitionistic fuzzy number for group decision making, *Applied Mathematical Modelling* 38 (2014) 2969-2982.
- [77] L.A. Zadeh, *Fuzzy Sets, Information and Control*, 8, 338-353, 1965.
- [78] X. Zhang, P. Liu, Method For Aggregating Triangular Fuzzy Intuitionistic Fuzzy Information and Its Application to Decision Making, *Technological and economic development of economy Baltic Journal on Sustainability*, 16/2 (2010) 280-290.
- [79] X. Zhang, F. Jin, P. Liu, A grey relational projection method for multi-attribute decision making based on intuitionistic trapezoidal fuzzy number, *Applied Mathematical Modelling* 37 (2013) 3467-3477.
- [80] X. Z. Wang, H. J. Xing, Y. Li, Q. Hua, C. R. Dong, and W. Pedrycz (2015) A Study on Relationship between Generalization Abilities and Fuzziness of Base Classifiers in Ensemble Learning. *IEEE Transactions on Fuzzy Systems*, 23(5): 1638-1654.
- [81] X. Z. Wang, R. A. R. Ashfaq, and A. M. Fu (2015) Fuzziness Based Sample Categorization for Classifier Performance Improvement. *Journal of Intelligent and Fuzzy Systems*, 29(3): 1185-1196.
- [82] H.Y. Zhang, J.Q. Wang, X.H. Chen, (2015) An outranking approach for multi-criteria decision-making problems with interval-valued neutrosophic sets, *Neural Computing and Applications*, DOI: 10.1007/s00521-015-1882-3.
- [83] H.Y. Zhang, P. Ji, J.Q. Wang, X.H. Chen, An improved weighted correlation coefficient based on integrated weight for interval neutrosophic sets and its application in multi-criteria decision-making problems, *International Journal of Computational Intelligence Systems*, 8(6) (2015) 1027-1043.

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Table 1. The decision matrices of decision maker d_k .

$$\begin{aligned}
 [\tilde{a}_{ij}^1]_{5 \times 4} &= \left(\begin{array}{cc}
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.5, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9); 0.5, 0.6, 0.7 \\ (0.4, 0.5, 0.7, 0.8); 0.3, 0.2, 0.3 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.1, 0.3, 0.4, 0.7); 0.4, 0.9, 0.3 \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.8); 0.7, 0.4, 0.2 \end{array} \right) \\
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.5, 0.6, 0.7, 0.8); 0.2, 0.7, 0.2 \\ (0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7); 0.2, 0.5, 0.4 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.1, 0.1, 0.4, 0.5); 0.1, 0.4, 0.3 \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.9); 0.5, 0.5, 0.6 \end{array} \right) \\
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.3, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7); 0.2, 0.5, 0.4 \\ (0.1, 0.1, 0.8, 0.9); 0.7, 0.5, 0.3 \\ (0.3, 0.4, 0.7, 0.8); 0.7, 0.4, 0.6 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 0.8); 0.1, 0.8, 0.3 \\ (0.2, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9); 0.4, 0.5, 0.3 \\ (0.1, 0.3, 0.4, 0.8); 0.5, 0.8, 0.3 \end{array} \right) \\
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7); 0.4, 0.7, 0.3 \\ (0.1, 0.3, 0.4, 0.7); 0.5, 0.8, 0.2 \\ (0.3, 0.4, 0.4, 0.8); 0.1, 0.5, 0.4 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7); 0.7, 0.4, 0.3 \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7); 0.7, 0.4, 0.1 \\ (0.1, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3); 0.5, 0.1, 0.3 \end{array} \right)
 \end{array} \right) \\
 [\tilde{a}_{ij}^2]_{5 \times 4} &= \left(\begin{array}{cc}
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.1, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5); 0.8, 0.4, 0.7 \\ (0.3, 0.4, 0.7, 0.8); 0.2, 0.4, 0.8 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.8); 0.8, 0.4, 0.3 \\ (0.3, 0.4, 0.7, 0.9); 0.7, 0.9, 0.3 \end{array} \right) \\
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9); 0.5, 0.1, 0.3 \\ (0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7); 0.6, 0.4, 0.5 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9); 0.3, 0.4, 0.3 \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.7, 0.8); 0.7, 0.8, 0.3 \end{array} \right) \\
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.1, 0.1, 0.4, 0.8); 0.3, 0.4, 0.2 \\ (0.1, 0.1, 0.8, 0.9); 0.3, 0.3, 0.3 \\ (0.6, 0.7, 0.7, 0.8); 0.8, 0.5, 0.7 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.2, 0.2, 0.5, 0.6); 0.2, 0.3, 0.1 \\ (0.6, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9); 0.3, 0.5, 0.6 \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5); 0.2, 0.2, 0.4 \end{array} \right) \\
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.7); 0.7, 0.4, 0.3 \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.7); 0.3, 0.9, 0.3 \\ (0.10.3, 0.4, 0.8); 0.5, 0.4, 0.9 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.7); 0.4, 0.4, 0.3 \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.6, 0.7); 0.5, 0.6, 0.3 \\ (0.1, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3); 0.4, 0.5, 0.9 \end{array} \right)
 \end{array} \right) \\
 [\tilde{a}_{ij}^3]_{5 \times 4} &= \left(\begin{array}{cc}
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.1, 0.1, 0.2, 0.5); 0.5, 0.9, 0.9 \\ (0.3, 0.4, 0.7, 0.8); 0.5, 0.1, 0.3 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.8); 0.1, 0.6, 0.3 \\ (0.4, 0.4, 0.7, 0.9); 0.5, 0.3, 0.9 \end{array} \right) \\
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.1, 0.1, 0.1, 0.4); 0.4, 0.7, 0.8 \\ (0.4, 0.5, 0.8, 0.9); 0.5, 0.4, 0.3 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.1, 0.1, 0.1, 0.4); 0.8, 0.6, 0.8 \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.7, 0.8); 0.5, 0.4, 0.9 \end{array} \right) \\
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.3, 0.3, 0.4, 0.8); 0.5, 0.2, 0.3 \\ (0.4, 0.5, 0.8, 0.9); 0.8, 0.7, 0.3 \\ (0.3, 0.5, 0.7, 0.8); 0.5, 0.4, 0.3 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.2, 0.2, 0.5, 0.8); 0.5, 0.7, 0.3 \\ (0.1, 0.1, 0.8, 0.4); 0.5, 0.9, 0.8 \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.7); 0.1, 0.6, 0.3 \end{array} \right) \\
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.2, 0.3, 0.7, 0.9); 0.1, 0.1, 0.3 \\ (0.4, 0.5, 0.8, 0.9); 0.5, 0.4, 0.3 \\ (0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.8); 0.1, 0.5, 0.3 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.1, 0.1, 0.2, 0.7); 0.5, 0.4, 0.3 \\ (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4); 0.5, 0.2, 0.4 \\ (0.1, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4); 0.5, 0.4, 0.8 \end{array} \right)
 \end{array} \right) \\
 [\tilde{a}_{ij}^4]_{5 \times 4} &= \left(\begin{array}{cc}
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.5, 0.7, 0.8, 0.9); 0.1, 0.9, 0.3 \\ (0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6); 0.5, 0.4, 0.3 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.2, 0.3, 0.5, 0.8); 0.5, 0.6, 0.6 \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.8); 0.1, 0.4, 0.8 \end{array} \right) \\
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4); 0.1, 0.2, 0.3 \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.7); 0.5, 0.6, 0.3 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.0, 0.1, 0.6, 0.7); 0.5, 0.7, 0.3 \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5); 0.5, 0.2, 0.4 \end{array} \right) \\
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.8); 0.5, 0.4, 0.3 \\ (0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.5); 0.5, 0.4, 0.3 \\ (0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 0.8); 0.5, 0.4, 0.3 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.1, 0.3, 0.7, 0.9); 0.5, 0.4, 0.3 \\ (0.1, 0.2, 0.5, 0.8); 0.2, 0.3, 0.6 \\ (0.1, 0.3, 0.4, 0.6); 0.3, 0.8, 0.5 \end{array} \right) \\
 \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.0, 0.1, 0.4, 0.7); 0.4, 0.7, 0.2 \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.6, 0.7); 0.6, 0.9, 0.3 \\ (0.4, 0.5, 0.7, 0.8); 0.2, 0.6, 0.5 \end{array} \right) & \left(\begin{array}{c} (0.4, 0.5, 0.8, 0.9); 0.5, 0.4, 0.8 \\ (0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.9); 0.5, 0.4, 0.3 \\ (0.0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3); 0.1, 0.4, 0.1 \end{array} \right)
 \end{array} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

Table 2. The ranking results of different methods.

Methods	Ranking results
<i>The proposed method with arithmetic operator</i>	$B_5 < B_2 < B_1 < B_4 < B_3$
<i>The proposed method with geometric operator</i>	$B_5 < B_2 < B_1 < B_3 < B_4$
<i>Ye's method [73] with geometric operator</i>	$B_5 < B_2 < B_3 < B_1 < B_4$
<i>Ye's method [73] with arithmetic operator</i>	$B_5 < B_2 < B_1 < B_4 < B_3$

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